

ART AND FAITH: DOCUMENTING THE PURPOSES OF ART FROM A
CONTEMPORARY CHRISTIAN PERSPECTIVE

by

Lea Emanuelli

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Approved by:

Date:

Christopher Slogar

5/15/24

Dr. Christopher Slogar, Department of Visual Arts

Stacy Mallicoat

5/24/2024

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director, University Honors Program

Introduction

“Now Bezalel and Oholiab, and every skillful person in whom the Lord has put skill and understanding to know how to perform all the work in the construction of the sanctuary, shall perform in accordance with all that the Lord has commanded” (Exodus 36:1-3).

This quote was the biblical source material for Pastor Martinez’s sermon in May of 2022. I had heard these verses before—God began preparations for the tabernacle, the divine dwelling place to be amongst His people. Pastor Martinez said, “The tabernacle was the only way people could meet with God.” He followed, “Art and beauty were made to glorify God.”

As I listened to that sermon, I sat back in surprise. Before that day, I had never heard a sermon that advocated for the arts in this way—for their beauty, for their cultural importance, for their God-ordained purpose. I hadn’t heard much about the arts at all, in fact.

Pastor Martinez then explained, “Here’s a misconception...when we exalt God’s word so much that He doesn’t care about visual beauty...but it doesn’t mean that God doesn’t want any art...It doesn’t mean that Christians are supposed to completely shun the arts, or that an artist’s trade is not a valid one in the Christian household. God cares about art. We’ve got to understand that art and beauty actually come from Him.”

As both a Christian and an Illustration major, I’ve always felt at peace with my artistic talents and my faith. My family has always supported my artistic inclination, from bequeathing me with a “drawing wall” of my childhood home that I soon filled with crayon scribbles, to buying countless sketchbooks as the pencil became my tool of choice, to buying easels and oil

paints, to supporting my decision to become a Studio Art major, and eventually, an Illustration major. Indeed, they've bridged the gap between religion and art in my life.

“And He has filled him [Bezalel] with the Spirit of God, in wisdom, in understanding and in knowledge and in all craftsmanship; to make designs for working in gold and in silver and in bronze, and in the cutting of stones for setting and in the carving of wood, so as to perform in every inventive work” (Exodus 35:31-33).

Certain aspects of that passage pique my interest; the fact that the Spirit of God gave Bezalel creative talents displays the validity of such pursuits, God sponsoring the creation of art exemplifies its importance in the world. Growing up in a supportive bubble like that, I didn't think much about the perceptions of art within the church until I was much older.

A phrase that I often hear in Christian circles is, “Church is a people, not a place.” While this statement is true in certain ways, as it emphasizes the importance of community over location, it also may induce or reflect the idea that buildings—and the art within them or inherently part of the architecture—are not important. From conversations I've had with people opposed to nude figure drawing classes to Christian colleges with no art program or no nude figure drawing classes within the art program, it is clear that there is a spectrum of ideas towards the arts within Christianity, ranging from hostile to accepting. As a Christian and an artist, my goal is to explore the ideas within Christianity towards the arts, particularly how Christian artists view their craft, in order to learn about their viewpoints regarding the purposes of art, and about how these artists seek to showcase these beliefs with their life's work.

Literature Review

Historically, the arts were closely tied to important institutions, such as the church and the courts (Stockenstrand & Ander, 2014). In a church setting, the visual arts were vital representations of biblical texts that instructed the illiterate majority of the population. However, in modern times, the arts have no such responsibility placed on them, and society's focus is on "monetary return," challenging "operations [that] are based on long tradition" (Stockenstrand & Ander, 2014).

The European Renaissance was tied to the Catholic church. During this era, artists were patronized by many church officials to decorate cathedrals with numerous paintings and sculptures. Much emphasis was placed on their idea of idealized human figures that referenced ancient Greek and Roman art, and there was a commonly held belief that youthful appearances and beauty correlated with sanctity (Corry, 2013). Then, when the Protestant Reformation occurred, the church's relationship with art shifted, largely taking a downward turn. Because Protestantism decreed that only the worship of God was fitting and that the veneration of icons, which they witnessed in the Catholic church, was immoral, many Protestants decided to participate in iconoclasm, or the destruction of images (Bremmer, 2008). However, the contrasting ideologies of Protestantism's many denominations contributed to a multitude of attitudes towards the arts.

Art was viewed differently within the Protestant church, but they mainly agreed that the veneration of icons was morally wrong. Jan N. Bremmer's "Iconoclast, Iconoclastic, and Iconoclasm: Notes Towards a Genealogy," provides information on the differences in denominations and how that affected their ideas towards the arts. While Martin Luther, the

founder of the Protestant Reformation and the origin of the Lutheran denomination, opposed the “veneration of images, he was fiercely against Bildersturm [the Great Iconoclasm] and in some ways rather favoured images in the church” (Bremmer, 2008). Luther’s viewpoint “created a climate that has led to the preservation of relatively much medieval art and liturgical objects in Lutheran churches” (Bremmer, 2008). This means that iconoclasm was limited within the Lutheran denomination; however, there was still a change in the way the arts were perceived. In contrast, King Henry VIII, the founder of Anglicanism, and King Edward VI, supported iconoclasm in a way that was “highly detrimental for the preservation of images, paintings, and liturgical vessels of silver and gold” (Bremmer, 2008). Yet still others had different ideas regarding the arts. According to Bremmer, John Calvin, the founder of Calvinism, and Huldrych Zwingli, the leader of the Reformation in Switzerland, “were very much against images in the churches, and that is why their followers in the Netherlands and Switzerland were the most radical in cleaning out the Calvinist churches” (Bremmer, 2008). While there are a multitude of Protestant denominations, these examples sufficiently display the spectrum of ideas related to the role of the arts in churches.

After the Protestant Reformation, iconoclasm ceased, but the relationship between art and the Protestant church was very different than that of the Catholic church. Tara Hamling provides vital insight into the post-Reformation view of the arts in household decoration in her work, “To See or Not to See? The Presence of Religious Imagery in the Protestant Household.” Hamling writes that, while it is “still widely assumed that post-Reformation Protestantism was fundamentally hostile towards religious imagery,” there were types of arts that were accepted within Protestantism (2007). This corroborates Bremmer’s research, which displayed that some denominations favored much of the arts; however, Hamling adds a new facet, displaying that

certain art styles, mediums, and subjects fit the Protestant creed more closely. According to Hamling's research, which revolves around several examples of decorative art in England and Scotland from the first half of the seventeenth century, domestic decoration seems to be a vital way to promote and regulate "godly" behavior in Protestant homes (2007). One example of such art is the carved wood and plasterwork screen in the Great Hall at Burton Agnes Hall in Yorkshire, which seems to have been a launchpad for discussion and a contributor to the atmosphere of the home (Hamling, 2007). Hamling has discussed common iconography and their themes, "identified the types of religious imagery displayed in large-scale domestic decoration," and that "certain materials, such as plasterwork, developed as a particularly appropriate art form for Protestant patrons" (2007). This was largely due to the fact that chimney-breasts were common sites for decorative artwork, and plasterwork was an effective medium to utilize there. Chimney areas were sites of household congregations, so artwork would serve as a source of discussion and contemplation (Hamling, 2007). Through Hamling's descriptions, it is clear that types of art were not only accepted, but welcomed within Protestant homes. These ideas also suggest that Protestants saw the arts in a particular way, as a vehicle to generate religious thoughts throughout the day. The arts were also used as a deterrent of unreligious behavior, as the presence of a religious figure could promote a constant vigilance of one's actions. Thus, Protestant ideas affected the way the arts were used and their role in domestic spaces, but whether this impact was positive or negative is contestable. According to Hamling, there was "a certain ambivalence around the power of the visual sense during [the first half of the seventeenth century]" (2007). Protestants viewed sight as "the most efficient of the bodily senses" and "feared the facility of their own sense of sight as a potential point of entry for sin and vice," including "covetousness, lust, greed, vanity, and idolatry" (2007). These ideas cannot be

immediately categorized as having a negative or positive effect on the arts; rather, they are a shift in ideas that marked a heightened awareness of the self, which came with the Reformation. On one hand, these ideas led to a plethora of domestic decorations that ensured one's sight was filled with religious teachings. On the other hand, fear of the potential pitfalls of sight corroborates the ideas that led some Protestants to rampant iconoclasm.

While there is debate regarding whether Protestant ideologies have positively or negatively affected the arts, scholar John D. Wilsey contrasts Hamling in providing decidedly positive examples of Protestantism and the arts. Through his work, "The Impact of the Reformation on the Fine Arts," Wilsey aims to display how the Protestant Reformation vitally influenced the way two seventeenth- and eighteenth-century artists, Johann Sebastian Bach and Rembrandt van Rjin, created art. Wilsey first discusses the purpose of art amongst Protestants, which was seen as a gift used to display beauty and not instruct the congregation or supplant Scripture (Wilsey, 2006). This viewpoint values the role of art as a God-given gift, while keeping art from superseding the role of canonical teachings, in order to respect Protestant theology. Overall, this version of Protestant beliefs is encouraging towards the arts, but retains some caution against them. Rembrandt, as Wilsey notes, focused on the individual's standing with God and painted realistic scenes from the Bible, which contrasted the Baroque paintings of the Catholic Counter-Reformation (Wilsey, 2006). Wilsey's work is important to the current project because he provides in-depth examples of historical ideologies, how they affected the arts, and how the purposes of art were directly linked to its acceptance in society. However, the fact that it is a case study means that Wilsey's findings are not necessarily indicative of the impact of the Reformation on all of the arts. The current project will solely focus on the visual arts, but contextualizing different art forms is still helpful to creating a full understanding of the past

circumstances. Overall, this work provides a persuasive counter-argument that paints the Reformation's effects on the arts in a positive light.

While there are numerous historical examples of both beneficial and detrimental views of the arts, these examples beg the question: What does Christian art look like today? To begin answering this question, it is first important to find out what types of art are produced today. Much of historical art, being tied to religious institutions, was religious in nature, but art from the Renaissance and after has expanded to include other subjects, such as the human figure, genre paintings, still lifes, landscapes, and more. Modern art includes the entertainment arts, installations, pop art, and abstract art, amongst other types, that exemplify the wide array of artistic styles. Therefore, there is less religious art today than in past centuries; moreover, contemporary artists that do use religious symbols oftentimes change the meanings of the original symbol (Kulikauskas, 2020).

Another important facet of contemporary Christian art is finding out where art is seen today. While art was relegated to the home or churches in the past, it is now also a part of museums and schools, especially colleges with art departments. However, there is little research on the current state of the arts in Christian spheres, perhaps reflecting an indifference for the arts.

Jonas Kulikauskas discusses the dwindling amount of Christian art in "Not of This World." While there are a few notable pieces of contemporary art that relate to Christianity in galleries, Kulikauskas noted that, even within Christian college campuses, the amount of faith-related art was limited. According to his studies, Biola University hosted an art exhibition in 2016 titled, "And Who is My Neighbor?" For this exhibit, the story of the Good Samaritan was allegedly the focal point; however, Kulikauskas notes that the works were not directly tied to the

theme, and were rather the “best match” for the stated theme (2020). This raises the question of whether the artists in the show created work that related to the theme in concept, not subject matter. Otherwise, Kulikauskas’s wording suggests that the artists did not have this theme in mind while creating, which presents the subsequent question of whether the artists were motivated by any religious concepts at all. Kulikauskas also described a lack of Christian art at a recent UCLA exhibition, but because UCLA is not religiously affiliated, a dearth of Christian art is not unexpected. However, a lack of Christian art at a Christian university is more surprising. This potentially reflects a disbelief in the compatibility of religion and the arts, despite religion historically being so closely tied to the arts.

How can we account for the scarcity of religious art at a religious school? Maybe we could explain it by stating that the fear of past icon worship may have eked into current beliefs. We could also speculate that many may not be concerned with the role of Christian art at all, believing it to be irrelevant within the church, home, school, or world, and instead utilize the many other, secular genres of art. Or yet, that people may believe that the arts are completely secularized and their purpose cannot be religious. It is difficult to find an explanation, as there is currently little research on Christians’ thoughts about the arts, especially on Christian college campuses.

Overall, the previously conducted secondary source research has made clear that the Protestant Reformation did mark a drastic change in the way the arts were viewed for many reasons, and the changes sparked were both positive and negative. The Reformation changed the way Protestants viewed the arts in the following ways: firstly, the visual arts were no longer the key form of storytelling as literacy rose. Secondly, according to Bremmer, the veneration of icons was seen as blasphemous, leading to either iconoclasm, in certain denominations, or

ambivalence towards art and the sense of sight in general. Thirdly, as Hamling displayed, certain types of art were promoted within Protestant households as a way to encourage religious ideas. Fourthly, as Wilsey explains, the Reformation spurred the paintings of Rembrandt, which has provided the world with a richness of paintings. Lastly, as Kulikauskas posits, contemporary Christian art can be scarce, even within Christian circles.

The majority of literature in this area concerns historical ideas of religious art, leaving most of contemporary religious art rarely explored. My thesis project aims to fill the gap of projects in Christian art, particularly examining the views of current Christian artists regarding the purposes of art. Thus, the purpose of this project is to answer the questions: What are the purposes of art, from the lens of current Christian artists? How does faith influence art, and vice versa? My goal is to lend an ear to the artists, not just the governments or authorities in power, but to allow those who create and practice art to dissect its purposes. In answering these primary questions, I am to explore how the current views on the purposes of art reflect the artists' ideologies and goals, as well as the cultural climate.

Introduction to Methodology

In order to answer my primary questions, I have listed a sequence of steps, including: (1) collecting data via conducting interviews, and transcribing, synthesizing, and analyzing interviews, and (2) curating a list of Christian professional artists' works and writings, and subsequently analyzing the content as it relates to the primary and secondary questions. For the purposes of this project, the basic category of Christianity includes both Protestants and Catholics.

I have conducted interviews of art majors from both California State University, Fullerton, and Biola, including any concentrations within the Art major, in order to gain information on the perspectives of different kinds of art students. I have also curated a selection of Christian professional artists, in order to analyze their artworks alongside written statements of faith, including self-written statements and statements from interviews.

For both interviews and content analysis, I am utilizing qualitative information. For interviews specifically, I will largely use qualitative information that falls under the field of ethnography, particularly ethnographic interviews. Lina Lee writes, “Ethnography offers us the chance to step outside of our narrow cultural backgrounds...to apprehend the world from the viewpoint of other human beings who live by different meaning systems” (Lee, 2012). Lee continues to describe ethnography, writing that the field “relies primarily on an in depth understanding of the values, beliefs, and attitudes underlying the behaviors of others through first-hand observations (Lee, 2012). According to researchers led by Westby, “the goal of ethnographic interviewing is for the [interviewee] to provide a vivid description of their life experiences” (2003). De Leon and Cohen similarly state that the goal of ethnographic interviews is to learn more about the informant (2005). As these researchers have discussed, ethnography is particularly useful when learning about a people-centered phenomenon. The field has been tailored to understanding the ideologies and experiences of those being interviewed. While this study draws heavily upon ethnography, the goal proceeds one step further than learning about the interviewee’s experiences, aiming to induce critical thinking about art.

As mentioned in the literature review, contemporary Christian art is not often studied. It is even less common to utilize ethnography in this field. In addition, ethnography is a field commonly associated with anthropology and intercultural studies, as well as in healthcare, as it is

a tool that provides insight into the thoughts of patients and clients, including the families of those with communicative disorders. This particular project, which falls under the fields of art history and religious studies, will use an ethnographic approach to cause the interviewee to think more deeply about the role of religious art, and ultimately aims to learn about, document, and learn from others' opinions and beliefs.

Step 1: Interviews

The most informative part of this research study will consist of conducting structured or semi-structured interviews, utilizing ethnography as a guide. The goal of this set of interviews is to document the beliefs of current Christian art majors from both CSUF and Biola, creating an oral history in order to gain a greater understanding of these artists' beliefs that motivate their works, as well as how their ideologies inform and interact with their art, their audiences, and their own artistic journeys.

To begin this process, I reached out to Biola's Visual Arts department to obtain permission to interview art students. Ultimately, I was recommended to provide an advertisement for my project, which was sent in the Biola Art department newsletter. I created a digital flyer titled, "Art + Faith Interviews," and briefly discussed my project, methods and information privacy, contact information, incentives, and provided a link to a google form that served as my consent form. This distribution of information ensured that each student had standardized and minimal information about the study, in order to minimize bias and their pre-interview preparation. Each participant was interviewed once, which parallels Nadan's study (2019).

Before beginning the interview process, I created a list of interview questions. I asked similar questions to all interviewees, mainly derived from the premade list. However, not all

questions were asked, especially since some artists would answer more than one question unintentionally within answers. In addition, in order to account for the flow of the conversation, and for new and previously unexpected information, I also asked different follow-up questions that were tailored to interviewees' responses. Therefore, not all questions were the same across all interviewees. I refrained from asking interviewees questions about the artwork present on campus, as this may cause bias to answer favorably when pressured by the proximity of the artwork and school pride.

The questions included basic, descriptive, and structural categories. According to Westby, Burda, and Mehta, ethnographic interviews employ descriptive questions, which are broad and allow the interviewee to describe their experiences, daily activities, and those they encounter (2003). Structural questions are responses to descriptive ones, providing insight into how the interviewee "organizes knowledge" (Westby et al., 2003). This study first employed descriptive questions about the participant's experiences and practices as an artist, then delved into the structural questions pertaining to their ideologies and art processes.

My list of questions includes, but is not limited to, the following:

1. Tell me about what inspired you to become an artist.
 - Give me an example of ___. (If they say, "I love art," ask for an example of art styles/eras that they love, etc.)
2. Tell me about your goals as an artist. How has this changed throughout your life?
3. What difficulties have you experienced as an artist? *
 - Difficulties in expressing yourself, finding your style, finding a career path, facing societal undervaluing of the arts, etc.?

- What has helped you during those times?
4. Do you have a purpose as an artist?
 - Does your faith/being a follower of Christ impact your art?
 - What has led you to these beliefs?
 - Has a biblical passage inspired your beliefs?
 - Do you have a set process for every art piece, or does it change every time?
Where is your process on that spectrum?
 5. Does art have a purpose?
 - Do you think art has a spiritual purpose?
 - What has led you to these beliefs?
 - Have you seen examples of Christian art that have stood out to you? Why?
 6. What message do you aim to convey with your art? (Specific pieces or as a whole)
 7. What art eras/styles do you love? Why? *
 8. Tell me what you think about the iconography of Christian art.
 - Does a particular era speak to you (Renaissance, modern, etc.)?
 - Do you create religious art?
 - Do you think it affects the art scene today? Does it affect the way you think about art?
 9. Are there any Christian artists who inspire you?
 10. Who is your audience?

As seen in this list, each numbered question is broader than the sub-questions under it. This is to adhere to ideals in ethnographic interviews, which seek to maximize participants' speaking and minimize bias from the interviewer (De Leon and Cohen, 2005). However, if participants

find it difficult to speak to their experiences, or need a guiding example to understand the question, more specific sub-questions are efficient ways to promote further thought.

Questions marked with an asterisk were considered to be of lower importance. As the goal was to learn about each artist's personal ideologies, all questions aimed to stimulate conversation. If an artist had difficulty in answering ideological questions, the questions marked with an asterisk would be used to provide a different avenue of thought that may lead to a discussion of the artist's ideas and experiences.

The purpose of these question types and utilizing ethnographic interviewing in general is to generate the most conversation with the least possible bias. As De Leon and Cohen state, "The most valuable probing techniques are those that stimulate or encourage an informant to provide data on specific topics with minimal influence from the interviewer" (2005).

Interviews were approximately 15-30 minutes long and the audio was recorded for optimal transcription accuracy. Four interviews were conducted; the number was not previously determined, and entirely hinged on the number of volunteers.

After transcribing interviews, I recorded the major themes from each student, and cross-referenced them to determine whether any overarching themes appeared. Interview synthesis and analysis was based on two factors: (1) Overlapping ideologies, and (2) the importance of/emphasis on ideologies. Therefore, not all major themes discussed were held by all students interviewed, but they were emphasized by students that cared deeply about the idea.

Interviews were very comprehensive on ideas regarding the purposes of art, the art that each student produces, personal artistic goals, personal experiences, and stylistic preferences.

Therefore, the discussion portion of this project mainly synthesizes interviewees' statements, rather than adding to their statements.

Step 2: Content Analysis

In order to answer my primary questions, I have also chosen five Christian professional artists, whose artworks and written statements of faith, including self-written statements and statements from interviews, have been analyzed.

This section is separated into two parts: (1) biographical information on each artist, and (2) analysis of themes. Firstly, I will provide a snapshot of each of the five artists that I have selected: Makoto Fujimura, Kent Twitchell, Lynn Aldrich, Michael Dudash, and Ron DiCianni. This section will provide not only brief biographical information and an overview of the artist's work, but will also answer the following questions: What is the purpose of art? How does faith influence art, and vice versa? How does the artist's work display their ideologies?

Answers to the secondary questions are woven throughout the first and second parts of this section. Secondary questions include: How overtly spiritual is their work? (1) Who is the intended audience? (1a) Does this artist consider himself/herself an evangelist? (1b) Is this work accessible to mainstream audiences, or is it intended for those who already possess knowledge of its subject matter? (2) How controversial is this artist's work? Is it meant to cause strong emotions or to be easily digestible?

Secondly, I will analyze important themes that run throughout one or more of these artists' statements and work. Themes have been chosen based on the following criteria: (1) How important these themes are to answering the primary and secondary questions, (2) How

important these themes are to the artist(s), and (3) How unique and helpful these themes are to the process of artmaking.

Discussion

Upon analysis of art student interviews and professional artists' content, I have created two lists of themes. The first list, which stems from the interviews, contains three themes, which include the following: (Theme A) Art as a means of understanding transcendence and/or the divine, (Theme B) Art as a means of building up, not solely tearing down, and (Theme C) Art as a catalyst for asking questions, rather than providing answers. The second list, comprised of the professional artists' artworks and statements of faith, contains four themes, which includes the following: (Theme A) Art as a means of integrating faith into the world, (Theme B) Art can be utilized as a study of natural theology, (Theme C) Art is a byproduct of one's worldview, and Theme D: Art can be utilized as an evangelism tool. Sub-themes are also present for many of these themes and are exemplified within interviewee responses.

Through these four interviews, I was able to speak with a varied group of artists: two freshmen, two seniors; an Art Therapy major, Design, Painting, and Graphic Design. Their range of artistic and career goals were all different, from becoming an elementary school teacher, to an architect, to a fine artist, to a professional graphic designer.

Art Students' Themes relating to the Purpose of Art:

Theme A: Art as a means of understanding transcendence and/or the divine.

Sub-themes: (1) Theology, (2) Natural theology, (3) Art as a devotional practice, (4)

Exercise our humanity.

Interviews with Students 2, 3, and 4 point to a purpose of art as a means of understanding transcendence and/or the divine. In other words, there are aspects of the universe that are more divine than our lives, and art is a way to understand and express that.

According to Student 2 and 4, the purpose of art is to point to God, which is a vital aspect of understanding transcendence. Student 2 stated, "I don't think I'd be an artist if I weren't a Christian. Just 'cause I kind of think that art is pointless without Christianity. It's just...if it's separate from a transcendent good and a transcendent, capital 'B' Beauty, that all that we do on earth is connected to, it's pointless and it's just kind of like, wishy-washy self-expression." In other words, there is a higher purpose to art than reflecting on ground-level humanity; pointing upwards is vital. The avoidance of art that solely serves the purpose of self-expression ultimately leads to art with a purpose larger than oneself, which leads to the good of others.

Student 2, who is passionate about classical architecture and its usage for the good of society, stated, "Because it's all pointing upwards. It's all supposed to praise God, and the arches and the stained glass; there's a very intentional purpose to why it looks that way." He continued, "I try to convey...there's a higher order to things. There's a beauty that is above your ability to express yourself."

When I asked what, such as a Bible passage, led Student 2 to his belief that his art is impacted by his faith, he responded, "Reading the Pentateuch, Genesis and Exodus and

Leviticus, there's a bunch of talk in there, first about God creating, and how we should imitate God in certain ways, and then how God commands people like Bezalel in the Bible to create beautiful things for the tabernacle." Interestingly, I noted the passage with God's commandment to Bezalel in the introduction of this project, which is found in Exodus 35. Overall, Christian artists' beliefs are supported by biblical evidence of their worth. The study of theology, which is ultimately the study of God, impacts how artists see their act of creating, and ultimately, how they view the God they serve.

Student 4 similarly described religious art as "any art that has a deeper meaning, or points to higher." Notably, Student 4 referred to artwork with clear religious imagery, and created such work herself. When I asked why Student 4 became an artist, she answered, "I think religious art plays a big [part] in it, actually. Because growing up, we don't have anything on our walls besides family photos and religious art. So, religious art is something that I'm surrounded by all the time." To provide further detail on the type of religious art present in her home, Student 4 notes that, during her childhood, "I feel like my parents were always like, 'Oh, why don't you do a saints coloring page?'" This presence of and type of religious art has been a through line in the life of Student 4, so the connection between art and the divine was very natural and obvious.

Now, Student 4 creates work with clear religious imagery. I asked Student 4, "You mentioned that you know that your religious beliefs will play into your artistic creations. What has led you to these beliefs? Was there a particular Bible passage, or was it more like the prayer and discernment that you mentioned, or both?" Student 4 provided an example of an artwork she created, stating, "I think it was mostly prayer and discernment... I was reading the Bible passage, I think it's from Matthew, it was Jesus falling asleep in the boat, and then waking up and then calming the storm...I was just kind of reflecting on that Bible passage, and I had this like image

of Jesus asleep in the boat and He was holding me in His arms, and we were both just asleep, and His invitation was just like, ‘Fall asleep with me in the boat.’” To further elucidate the meaning of her idea, Student 4 explained that the purpose was “to trust Him through the storm, and trust and know that...He’s holding on to me and just having that invitation just to be okay...He’s acknowledging that the storm is there, but that it’s okay for me to fall asleep in His arms.” Student 4’s work is a very tangible way to understand the divine; viewers are called to place greater trust in their faith, and to be comforted by Christ, thus understanding His character in more depth.

Art is also seen as a means of exercising our humanity, which may be considered one of the most divine aspects of human existence. Student 3 described a purpose of art as “a really wonderful way...to ‘exercise my humanity.’” Similarly, Student 2 elaborated on this idea: “There’s a clear, inherent good to creating art as Christians, and God creates, and there’s something about creating that we’re supposed to do as humans...it almost makes us more human and fulfills...part of what our function is: to create. So, I think just studying God’s creation and studying the laws of proportion and line and all these things are inherently good things that’s worthwhile.”

As previously mentioned, the study of theology is important to understanding divinity through artwork. As Student 2 mentioned, “studying the laws of proportion and line” are also vital, which are considered natural theology, or inferences about the divine made by the study of the natural world.

Student 3, in particular, is creating a body of work that utilizes natural theology. Student 3 said, “I also feel a bit more of a desire to be more open with the Christian influence in my work—and I’m not painting, like, religious scenes. I’m painting shells and dead flowers, and

things like that. But referencing some spiritualities or spiritual realities—and I have a lot of like, death and resurrection imagery in my work.” Even seemingly mundane, yet beautiful, objects from nature can reflect and lead viewers to contemplate transcendence, as a dead flower can represent more than itself, such as the life cycle, as well as symbolize the death and resurrection of Christ. Ultimately, there is a conversation happening between art and faith, artist and artwork, audience and everything included.

Theme B: Art as a means of building up, not solely tearing down.

Sub-theme: Countercultural for the sake of hope.

Art is, in many ways, a mode of communication with others. According to Students 1, 2, and 3, a major purpose of art is to communicate a message that, at its core, builds people up and provides good. This ideology is countercultural, not for the sake of mere rebellion, but for the sake of helping a society that is lacking encouragement.

In 2 Corinthians 13:10, Paul writes, “For this reason I am writing these things while absent, so that when present I *need* not use severity, in accordance with the authority which the Lord gave me for building up and not for tearing down” (NASB, 1995). In Paul’s case, he wrote to instruct and encourage the church of the Corinthians, in the hopes that his words would compel them to holiness, so there would not be reason to tear them down. In this view, when injustice runs rampant in the world, it must be torn down. However, leaving the world in ruins and rubble is hardly productive, so building it back up is the goal.

Student 3 noted, “I think there’s a lot about the art world that’s like, tearing down some things right now, and I think our culture at large is doing that, which I guess sort of makes sense, but I think there’s a point at which the tearing down is going to be just total destruction, and

somebody needs to come in and kind of be like, 'Let's build this up!' And like, 'Here's a positive and affirmative thing about the world!' So, I really want to be doing that with the work that I make." Student 3 continued, describing that, currently, art is "being used to promote justice, that seeks to just expose injustice, which is important, and something that we ought to do as Christians: recognize injustice, repent from our sins...But the way of Christ is also to redeem, and we serve a creator God who makes all things new, and so He doesn't just destroy evil, He redeems. And I think the hope that we have in Christ is the thing that lets us recognize injustice and not despair about the world."

Student 2 stated, "I really feel like I see a real need for beauty in society that's lacking, and I think there's a purpose for people who, you know, want to bring back beauty." A major inspiration of Student 2 is Roger Scruton, a major proponent of beauty, especially in and through architecture, as a contributor of good to society.

Student 1, who is studying art therapy and whose goal is to become a preschool teacher, stated, "He [God] wants me to care for others." Student 1 explained that, while everyone is called to care for others, art is a particular way to create "something that other people can connect to," and that art is a means to that end. Student 2 stated a similar sentiment previously, in that art has a higher purpose than mere self-expression.

In a similar vein, Student 3 noted, "I just see a lot of...anger and strife and hopelessness and inability to reconcile, that I think maybe is [an] unavoidable cultural moment...but I also want to be able to respond to that with, like, 'Yes, there's injustice, but also redemption is the ultimate thing, and hope is the ultimate thing.'"

Theme C: Art as a catalyst for asking questions, rather than providing answers.

Sub-theme: Religious imagery need not be present to create an artwork with spiritual influence and meaning.

Art is a means by which to stimulate thought. Ideally, art encapsulates the process of engaging the viewer, presenting an idea, and influencing subsequent thoughts, anywhere on the spectrum from first asking a question to finally finding an answer. The best art incurs thoughts that linger long after the artwork itself is viewed.

In the same vein, art does not have to be visibly spiritual, or contain overt religious imagery, to be full of spiritual influence and/or meaning. Because art is a catalyst for asking questions, it need not present concrete, religious answers, but rather provide a launch pad for the viewer's own journey, spiritual or not.

According to Student 3, "art is so much more about asking questions than it is about giving answers, and so—it can be really easy, I think, for Christians to...be like, 'I know the answer because I have the hope! And I want you guys to have the hope, too!'" In general, Christians refer to salvation as "the hope," since it is a hope for eternal life, perfect goodness, and fellowship with God. Student 3 adds that many Christian artists think, "'I'm going to put the hope in the painting!' But it's like, nobody looking at the painting wants the answer; they want to ask the questions."

In the eyes of Student 3, sticking answers into paintings defeats the purpose of art as a mental exercise and a road to understanding. The emphasis is on art as part of the journey, not the end goal. However, rather than ending there, Student 3 also provides insight into how to create effective art. Her own current body of work revolves around the question, "Why do we

take things and hold them for ourselves? What draws us to those things?" Thus, Student 3's work reflects a desire to stimulate the mind to questions and exploration.

As an artist, art is about asking questions and figuring out how to best represent it in work. Student 3 stated, "How can you put the hope in the painting in a way that feeds the curiosity and inspires the imagination towards something good, instead of just saying, 'This is it. This is what you've been looking for.' It's like, well, they need to be able to find that on their own." Student 3 also implies that a painting cannot cause someone to become part of the faith; salvation comes from Christ alone. Therefore, a painting cannot equal salvation; as Student 3 notes, "to think that a painting that I make could save a person, that's just...insane." Ultimately, to Student 3, art is not effective when it presents an answer and thus, lacks a spark of curiosity; art is a useful tool to spur questions.

This led into Student 3's question, "To what extent does my faith need to be obviously present in my work?" Both Student 3 and I agreed that it is a long and sometimes difficult journey to determine how to best represent an integral part of ourselves in our work. This journey is also hampered by those who keep their faith and their work very separate. Student 3 noted, "And some of the best art made by Christians is made by Christians...who are not so forthright about the fact that they're Christian, and so it can be easily to separate—like, there's my art, and there's my faith, and I can live in my faith behind closed doors, but when I'm in the art world, I'm just an artist; I'm not a Christian, per se. Or that's not a part of myself that I talk about. And I just feel like they're so deeply intertwined and so equally—well, I'm more a Christian than I am an artist, and so I can't be in the art world and deny that part of myself."

In order to live out this ideology, Student 3's artworks stem from the desire to allow faith to influence art. Student 3 stated, "I also feel a bit more of a desire to be more open with the

Christian influence in my work—and I’m not painting, like, religious scenes. I’m painting shells and dead flowers, and things like that. But referencing some spiritualities or spiritual realities—and I have a lot of like, death and resurrection imagery in my work, and so...when I’m talking about it with people, it’s [clear that]...this is what I’m thinking about when I’m making this.”

Similarly, Student 1 mentioned a recent artwork that she made, in which “the background was kind of like a letter, like a prayer to God, but it was blurred because it was like, a personal thing...the piece itself wasn’t religious.” When I asked if, based on this personal artwork, she believes art must have religious imagery to be considered religious, she responded, “You [the audience] don’t necessarily see it as religious, but to me, it’s like an intimate [part of a] conversation with God.” Through this information, it is clear that the creation of art is multifaceted, in both the way that these artists’ faith influences their artworks, and in the subject matter that they create. Therefore, artworks that do not overtly display religious imagery still retain a conceptual depth, as well as complexity of content, as representing divinity through metaphor adds a degree of separation and more room for exploration.

Insight into Five Artists

1. Makoto Fujimura

The first such artist is Makoto Fujimura, whose work stems from his theme of “slow art,” which is characterized by its “process driven” and “refractive” nature (Fujimura, 2024a).

Fujimura’s body of work combines fine art and abstract expressionism, as well as the traditional Japanese art styles of “*Nihonga* and *Kacho-ga* (bird-and-flower painting tradition)” (Fujimura, 2024a). This multicultural art style, inspired by multiple art eras, with Fujimura’s idea of “slow art” at its core, all combine to create Fujimura’s unique stamp on the art world.

Makoto Fujimura studied at Bucknell University, eventually studying at Tokyo University of the Arts for a doctorate painting program (2024a). Fujimura's work from the past two decades can be identified by its large swaths of pigment, with a carefully nuanced balance of bright, bold colors and delicate modulation of hues and textures. Most works are abstract, many haunted by the vestiges of forms that could exist in our physical world.

Varying in theme, some works, describe the turmoil that followed 9/11 survivors. Other works reference traditional Japanese painting techniques and yet others reference his faith, or any combination of these elements (Fujimura, 2024a).

As an example of his faith-based art, Fujimura was commissioned to create his *Four Holy Gospels* series by Crossway for the four-hundred-year commemoration of The King James Bible in 2011 (Fujimura, 2024b). Fujimura created one work for each of the four Gospels, as well as a title work to unite them all, titled *Charis-Kairos*, or The Tears of Christ (Figure 1). With this set of artworks, Fujimura's goal was to display "the greater reality that the Bible speaks of... for the pure sake of integrating faith and art in our current pluralistic, multicultural world" (Fujimura, 2024b). Fujimura was interested in creating an "unprecedented marriage of a modern, usually secular art form with ancient scripture" through his work, resulting in the series of images that doubtlessly combine modern style with ancient symbolism (Fujimura, 2024b).

2. Kent Twitchell

The second artist is muralist Kent Twitchell, an artist whose monumental, hyperrealistic works have illuminated entire buildings throughout Los Angeles. He is considered "the dean of mural art in Los Angeles, itself widely considered the mural capital of the United States" (Hinch, 2016). Kent Twitchell's work is largely counter-cultural and guided by his religious beliefs, as

his art is “public-spirited, representational, addressing religious themes, and by virtue of its medium unavailable for sale in today’s high-rolling art market,” which, as Hinch notes, “goes against just about every artistic trend of the years Twitchell has been at work” (2016). Twitchell has described in various ways that he sees his faith “as a quest to encounter, and to represent in works of art, the unchanging truth of God” (Hinch, 2016).

An artist since before he started kindergarten, Twitchell graduated high school with the ambitions of becoming a commercial artist and enlisted in the military to become an Air Force illustrator (Hinch, 2016). His first assignments included painting “Plexiglas screens used to plot the position of aircraft at navigation centers,” then “illustrating briefing papers used by generals” (Hinch, 2016). However, after gaining experience in the art field, Twitchell decided to pursue a formal education in the arts. In 1972, Twitchell graduated from Cal State L.A. with an art degree, and then from Otis with a Masters in Fine Art in 1977 (Hinch, 2016).

Twitchell’s art varies in concept and content, depending on the commissioner, but figures are usually the subject matter, and his style is representational. For example, his mural, *Harbor Freeway Overture* from 1993 (Figure 2), depicts most of the Los Angeles Chamber Orchestra of that time and has no known religious themes.

However, many of his works do include religious themes, while the presence of religious imagery varies by piece. One notable mural, *The Word* (Figure 3), which stretches from the ground to the top of a building at Biola, clearly depicts Jesus, robed in red and white, holding a Bible, with two shadows stretching to his left. While this piece displays clear religious imagery, the fact that its home is a Christian university means that it does not primarily function as an evangelism tool, as all students and faculty have at least some familiarities with the university’s ideology.

Many of Twitchell's works do appear within the public sphere, however. *111th Street Jesus* (Figure 4), *Holy Trinity with the Virgin* (Figure 5), and *Six Los Angeles Artists* (Figure 6) all faced thousands upon thousands of pairs of eyes through the years. The latter two murals depict Christian themes cloaked in the appearance of everyday people, displaying no overt religious imagery, while *111th Street Jesus* is a direct depiction of Jesus that parallels *The Word*, in both hair and robes.

3. Lynn Aldrich

A renowned contemporary sculptor, Lynn Aldrich surprisingly did not begin her career as an artist. Aldrich, who has loved learning since childhood, states, "I had a background in biology and worked in a virology laboratory (Aldrich, 2023). Besides this, Aldrich also earned her undergraduate degree in English (Aldrich: Storyboard). Although her drastic career changes may seem surprising, Aldrich ties all of these fields together with a common thread, stating, "All are fueled by an investigatory drive" (Storyboard).

Lynn Aldrich's sculptures are characterized by mundane objects, including, but not limited to, sponges, gutters, drywall panels, and brushes. For example, her sculpture, *Water Feature* (Figure 7), utilizes galvanized steel downspouts in silver and blue to create an organic, many-limbed shape that is reminiscent of a coral or waving anemone. Her goal is to use everyday items and "see if through slight manipulation or accumulation or re-presentation in a different context, a kind of revelation will occur" (Shorb, 2016).

While discussing her work with John Shorb, Lynn Aldrich emphasizes the idea of "hyperdesire" as the driving force behind her work, which she explains as "a longing that reaches past every other longing—absolutely nothing will satisfy it but God, himself" (2016). While

desires in general get us from point A to point B, as we desire to succeed in our careers or to complete basic chores, “hyperdesire” is a ceaseless undercurrent that draws us to something greater than ourselves.

Within her work, Aldrich’s main themes include the Incarnation. She further breaks down this idea into the elements of transcendence, or the transformation of something mundane into something divine, and the extravagant beauty of reality. These ideas stem from her identity as a Christian. Aldrich notes, “I want to look out at the world and engage with the reality of what exists. I think that includes aspects of theology—a parallel, transcendent, yet also real, universe, the Incarnation, the worth of human consciousness, the purpose of history. The extravagance of creation is called natural theology, I think—that all of nature is a text revealing God” (Shorb, 2016). Thus, many of her works refer back to flora and fauna and are in conversation with environmental issues.

Despite her emphasis on transcendence within her work, Aldrich seeks to remain firmly grounded as an artist, which extends to her usage of very mundane materials. She views art as a job, which people in every era worked in, and adds, “I try not to romanticize it” (Shorb, 2016). Dismissing the notion that artists work in a higher plane of existence, Aldrich states, “That’s one reason why I like Robert Smithson a lot. I love ‘Monuments of Passaic’ where Smithson goes out and declares the various rusty industrial ruins along the river as today’s grand monuments” (Shorb, 2016).

Aldrich’s work all stems from her faith; however, in contrast to many Christian artists, Aldrich does not insert religious imagery into her work. She comments, “I don’t set out to have Christian content, but I set out to be grounded in my worldview as a Christian” (Shorb, 2016). Therefore, her ideologies grow outward from belief to action, influencing her artwork from the

beginning, particle by particle, without needing to be visible in the concrete subject matter of her work.

4. Michael Dudash

With a distinct painting style that follows him through different subject matter and themes, Michael Dudash is an oil painter whose work has been defined by multiple ideas. For the majority of his painting career, a love for the old West, or the “great American frontier,” has been the focus of his work (Dudash, 2023). Dudash states, “I love the history, the characters, the costuming, the critters and the landscapes, and the ample opportunities that exist to tell a great story. The themes that permeate western art also feel like home to me – faith, family, friends, self reliance and hard work, just to name a few” (2023). Michael Dudash’s painting style is characterized by saturated colors, stark contrast between light and shadow shapes, and areas that emphasize sharp edges, with some accents of highly diffused, obscured objects.

Dudash’s career trajectory follows a unique path. After one year of college as an art major, Dudash quit school to become a musician, which lasted for six years. Then, he briefly went back to school at Minneapolis College of Art and Design (Dudash, 2023). Dudash was able to earn a living as a freelance illustrator and oil painter, working for clients such as Random House, Warner Bros. Nike, NBC, from 1977 to 2000. He was also a lecturer and instructor at many art schools and museums. However, in 2002, he decided to shift his career and become a fine artist (Dudash, 2023).

Although Dudash’s Western art is his main theme, he also presents collections of work focused on landscapes, still lifes, figurative work, and illustrations, as well as others. More recently, Dudash emphasized the importance of expressing his faith in his work, stating, “As the

years have gone by, the subject matter of my artwork has been centered more and more on Christian themes” (2023). Dudash adds, “I'm thankful for having the opportunity to use my abilities to spread the Gospel” (2023). Thus, for Dudash, art is an evangelism tool, which he uses by creating paintings with distinctly religious imagery.

This is not solely a recent development, however. No matter which collection of art Dudash’s audience sees, they will view a symbol of his faith. Presumably since he began his painting career, Dudash has added a cross to the end of his signature on his works. Dudash notes, “Having met the Lord 46 years ago, I wanted to make a statement about my faith as a born-again Christian, and this was what I decided upon” (2023). The sign of the cross is visible on his works of all subject matters.

Dudash’s accomplishments are numerous. His work has been featured in numerous solo and group exhibitions, and he has been the recipient of many awards since 1979, the most recent being the gold medal for “Best Oil Painting” from the Cowboy Artists of America in 2022 (Dudash, 2023).

5. Ron DiCianni

A skilled and renowned painter, Ron DiCianni’s self-proclaimed mission is to “Reclaim the Arts for Christ” (DiCianni, 2024). DiCianni’s illustrious career has spanned the commercial arts, painting, and murals. Currently, he sells original paintings and prints on his website, and has been commissioned by various organizations, secular and Christian alike. DiCianni generally creates prints from his paintings, meaning that he not only paints an image, but also creates and sells copies of a given artwork. This differs from fine artists who specifically sell the physical artwork with no reproductions.

As an art student, Ron DiCianni studied at the American Academy of Art in Chicago, after which he embarked on the path of commercial illustration. During this period of time, DiCianni gained a high-caliber clientele, including McDonald's (DiCianni, 2024). One of his most notable accomplishments includes being the Official Olympic Illustrator for the 1980 Olympics (DiCianni, 2024). It is inferable that DiCianni's art during his commercial illustration career was largely dictated by his clients, thus leading him to create art separate from his personal mission.

However, since 1989, DiCianni has been bold in creating faith-based artworks, beginning with a piece titled, "Spiritual Warfare." He has created many bodies of work since then, many of them revolving around different themes present in Christianity. His artworks typically contain bold religious imagery, often with depictions of Jesus, angels, and other faith-related topics. For example, DiCianni's painting, "Safely Home," a painting based on Peter 1:9 and containing the overt religious imagery of Christ and an angel comforting a previously desolate person, is a bold but welcoming image, potentially even for those outside of the faith who relate to the comforted person (2024). The accessibility of his work to mainstream audiences is not certain, and widely depends on the imagery utilized per painting and the audience that finds it; while mainstream audiences may admire the skill of his paintings and potentially connect with or become curious about the subject matter, his works could potentially seem unrelatable to others.

Theme A: Art is a means of integrating faith into the world.

Sub-theme: Art can be palatable to mainstream audiences without neglecting or exploiting its spiritual core.

Both Makoto Fujimura and Kent Twitchell utilize art as a means to seek and spread the truth, a way to integrate faith into the world. While some of Twitchell's art pieces boast clear

religious imagery, both he and Fujimura create work that refers to their Christian ideologies in concept, not outright content.

The way each artist achieves this goal shares parallels and distinct divergences.

Twitchell, a staunch hyperrealist, would likely disagree with Fujimura's abstract expressionist approach. Twitchell states, "Philosophically, I'm defending the fact that I'm more excited about doing realism. I couldn't get up in the morning if I was going to glorify the colors that a paint manufacturer did" (Hinch, 2016). While Twitchell's approach influences what he enjoys and values about art, it also influences how he presents art to the world. As a realist, his art projects a legible, nuanced, and seemingly complete image to the viewer, while retaining areas of intrigue.

In contrast, Fujimura is particularly enthralled with particular pigments and techniques, ultimately leading back to his process-driven approach, which values the effort and exploration of art over its final product. Fujimura regularly describes the pigments used under the title of his works; for example, Fujimura's *Walking on Water–Glacier* (Figure 9), is noted to be made of pulverized azurite and malachite (2024b). If Twitchell's artworks leave the viewer asking some questions and gaining some answers, Fujimura's work is more open-ended, leaving his viewers with distinctly unanswered questions.

As Twitchell states, "The most important thing we can do in fine art is to seek the truth" (Hinch, 2016). Both artists display a passion for presenting the truth of their faith in their works, and the process of asking questions and finding answers is vital to the search and its ultimate completion. Both artists utilize a subtlety in proclaiming their faiths, being both palatable to mainstream audiences and retaining spirituality at its core. According to Hinch, "Twitchell neither avoids nor exploits religious themes" (2016). This sentiment applies to both Twitchell and Fujimura, as the two artists create work that is welcoming to those who do or do not believe.

In addition, their works do not seek to elicit strong, negative emotional reactions; rather, Twitchell's work is full of non-aggressive figures, while Fujimura's abstract work contains subtle and calming color nuance. Twitchell's murals are free for the public to view, a natural sight when driving through L.A., while Fujimura's work allows his audience to seek its concepts or quietly pass by.

111th Street Jesus (Figure 4) had a warm smile and the relaxed, welcoming gesture of open arms. While many who see this mural may have divergent religious beliefs or be complete strangers to the Christian faith, *111th Street Jesus* had the air of an old friend welcoming one home. *Holy Trinity with the Virgin* (Figure 5) and *Six Los Angeles Artists* (Figure 6) both utilize regular people to represent the Holy Trinity and other biblical figures, displaying no overt religious imagery. In addition, these murals are inviting, with an air of intrigue, as the meaning of the work is not clearly spelled out. The figures merely face the viewers, offering few answers but welcoming all questions.

Fujimura's works, such as *Lux Aeterna – Hope* (Figure 10), and *Christmas 3020* (Figure 11), both boast his signature style of gently-shifting colors in abstraction, the wisps of forms resembling reality causing the viewer's mind to pause, double back, and search for the evasive meaning within the canvases (2024b). Both works refer to Fujimura's faith. For *Lux Aeterna – Hope*, inspired by Lauridsen's musical composition of a similar title, Fujimura writes, "Lauridsen's *Lux Aeterna* continued to hover over me and allowed me to move into my pain again...I hear the dissonance of brokenness, and yet, like gold in a Kintsugi bowl (venerable Japanese tea tradition of mending broken vessels with Japan lacquer and gold), mending to make New. In a particularized way, the music highlighted and captured a single line in John 11, the shortest sentence in the entire Bible. 'Jesus wept'" (Fujimura, 2024b).

Fujimura's *Christmas 3020*, created in 2020, also highlights his faith as a source of hope in times of despair. He writes, "Originally titled 'Christmas 2020,' I decided to retitle, desiring to infuse hope into the title itself - hope that the painting itself points to" (Fujimura, 2024b). He continues, "How could one paint anything joyous, and extravagant during such a time as this?...Painting, to me, is a prayer, asking the impossible questions in the midst of our 'Ground Zero' conditions of loss, to assume the abundance of beauty in the midst of scarcity" (Fujimura, 2024b).

Theme B: Art can be utilized as a study of natural theology.

"I want to look out at the world and engage with the reality of what exists" (Aldrich, 2023). Lynn Aldrich's words are mirrored in Kent Twitchell's statement, "I believe truth can be known and is meant to be known. Everything is not relative.... The symbolism of that is realism as opposed to a non-objective approach to art" (Hinch, 2016).

Both Aldrich and Twitchell look to the natural world to create their works. As Aldrich notes, the study of the natural world within the context of God as the creator of the natural world is natural theology.

According to philosophy professor Charles Taliaferro, "Natural theology is the practice of philosophically reflecting on the existence and nature of God independent of real or apparent divine revelation or scripture" (2009). This is often done through the development of "arguments about God based on the existence of the cosmos, the very concept of God, and different views of the nature of the cosmos, such as its ostensible order and value" (Taliaferro, 2009). For the purposes of this discussion, I will be discussing the usage of natural theology within the context

of Christianity; however, it is vital to note that the study of natural theology spans many religions and is even used by those who reject religious traditions (Taliaferro, 2009).

Kent Twitchell's realistic approach to murals rejects the "celebration of the universe as accident," which was a view shared by most of his art school professors and peers (Hinch, 2016). His clear forms of figures across his work, and especially seen in the figures of *Six Los Angeles Artists*, displays reverence for the complexity and nuance within the human figure, respect for the body, mind, and soul that indisputably ties a human together.

Aldrich takes a different, non-representational approach to her work that equally represents the idea of reflecting reality. This is seen in *Free Refill* (Figure 12), a tall, silver sculpture of galvanized steel downspouts, and *Biophilia* (Figure 13), a sculpture resembling undersea corals and other plants, which is made of sponges, scrubbers, plastic gloves, mop heads, among other items (Aldrich, 2023). In this way, Aldrich engages with reality by utilizing real items, allowing mundane objects to transcend into art, and displaying the duality of the everyday and the divine, which both exist in the same universe.

More than just acknowledging reality, though, both artists see reality as a reflection of a Creator. Much of Aldrich's work revolves around the idea of Incarnation, or a transcendent metaphor of mundane to divine. When she creates environmentalist sculptures, she not only wants to evoke care for the environment, but to reflect upon God as well. Aldrich states, "These pieces also celebrate the microcosm that is a coral reef, God's amazing extravagance, the gift of biodiversity" (Shorb, 2016). Twitchell notes that his art is "an outgrowth of [his] search for meaning," as each "person...has a vacuum inside that can only be filled by God" (Hinch, 2016).

Both Aldrich and Twitchell engage with the natural world to create their artworks, which are studies in natural theology, though very different in medium and subject matter. Their

artworks, through either manipulating physical objects or through representing complex human forms, both display God's multifaceted power as a creator. Faith influences art, and in these cases, leads to the creation of art that is an exploration of God's character in every brush stroke and found object.

Theme C: Art as a byproduct of one's worldview.

Sub-theme: (1) The metaphorical value of art can weigh more than its physical value. (2)

Art is a multidimensional process, not a mere object.

“I don't set out to have Christian content, but I set out to be grounded in my worldview as a Christian.” (Shorb, 2016). Lynn Aldrich's words display the ever-nuanced connection between art and faith, with art being a byproduct of her beliefs. In addition, her work, grounded in the manipulation of everyday objects, displays that the metaphorical meaning behind a work can be more important than its physical constituent parts. Moreover, Aldrich displays that art is more than a mere object, through her emphasis on her beliefs as the motivations that influence her work, whether visible or invisible.

Aldrich's ideology displays that the influence of faith on art does not need to be visible; rather, beliefs influence the kinds of actions we decide to take, and that leads to the creation of a physical art piece, one that may be devoid of overt religious imagery.

As a precursor to this statement, Aldrich notes, “I was continually struggling with where my faith might enter the work. I think that's a good place to be. I don't think we should make it any easier on ourselves—we should just jump in and expect that challenge. I want to engage what's out there—this is the time and place in which I live” (Shorb, 2016).

Much of her work reflects this notion. Aldrich's *Velvet Painting: Ascension* (Figure 14), a canvas covered in horizontal strips of velvet that create a sunset-like gradient that morphs from pitch black to deep purples, fiery pinks to yellows, symbolizes Christ's resurrection and subsequent ascension into heaven (Ollman, 2015). Aldrich is a master of the "transparent alchemy" of at once changing common objects into art pieces with precious symbolic significance, and allowing the objects to remain common (Ollman, 2015).

This rings true in much of Aldrich's work: at first glance, one sees the careful blending of a sunset, which, upon closer inspection, is clear to be composed of bits of fabric. *Hydra Hydrant* (Figure 15), a white, tree-like sculpture with a trunk and writhing, snakelike appendages, is made of ordinary plastic downspouts, elbows, leaf strainers, and gutter parts (Aldrich, 2023). Aldrich's ability to create a piece that seems full of movement, and is instead created from inorganic downspouts, displays her ability to both transform the ordinary into the extraordinary, and to dispel her illusion at will. Moreover, the symbolic representation of a modern hydra, an ancient Greek monster of legends, which boasted one head that, when cut off, sprouted two new ones, displays the depth of her work.

Renew Your Reef (Figure 16), for example, a sculpture that appears to be a vibrant, technicolor coral reef of sorts, is actually a careful composition of common objects, such as brushes, sponges, and even a plunger (Aldrich, 2023). However, even after the first and second analyses of the work, a third look is in order, as the symbolic and spiritual weight of this piece is monumental. In using cleaning products, Aldrich states, "I'm trying to say, let's clean up our oceans! These pieces also celebrate the microcosm that is a coral reef, God's amazing extravagance, the gift of biodiversity" (Shorb, 2016).

Theme D: Art can be utilized as an evangelism tool.

Sub-themes: (1) Through religious imagery, and/or (2) through religious concept. (3) Art is a means of creating a shared visual culture.

Perhaps most obviously, art is a clear method of evangelism, also known as a means of sharing and spreading the faith. Evangelism both informs recipients of vital points of the Christian faith and serves as a call to action for recipients to voluntarily join the community of faith. Michael Dudash sees his own art as an opportunity for evangelism. Dudash seeks out opportunities to imbue his art with his faith in a way that will be noticed by his audience, whether the particular painting does or does not have religious imagery.

On every painting, Dudash paints a cross next to his signature. Dudash states, “Having met the Lord 46 years ago, I wanted to make a statement about my faith as a born-again Christian, and this was what I decided upon” (Dudash, 2023). He notes that, throughout his career, “many clients and contacts have inquired about” the cross, which is a sign that his decision has successfully and significantly caught the attention of his audience (Dudash, 2023). For example, Dudash’s painting *Into an Autumn Wind* (Figure 17), which is part of his long-standing body of work on the western frontier that does not display religious content, presents a small symbol of the cross in the bottom right corner (2023).

Moreover, Dudash’s work has increasingly centered upon Christian themes and imagery (Dudash, 2023). His painting, *Watching their Flocks by Night* (Figure 18), is directly inspired by Luke 2:8, and displays a direct biblical scene of a group of shepherds in traditional clothing sitting around a campfire, with various shepherds and flocks of sheep scattered throughout the countryside, illuminated by the North Star (Dudash, 2023).

As described in the literature review, Christian art was historically used as a method of teaching biblical passages to a mainly illiterate population. In modern times, since a much larger percentage of the population is literate, Christian art that utilizes Christian imagery can further the cause of evangelists, spreading the word to peoples who know little or nothing about the faith.

Both Michael Dudash and Ron DiCianni describe the visual arts as a means to an end, their goal being to create a revival of Christian art that mirrors historical trends. Dudash describes his goals as he writes, “Today there are a number of very talented and accomplished contemporary artists, who as Christians are working to try and bring about a revival in artwork that expresses all aspects of the Christian faith” (2023). Similarly, DiCianni expresses a goal of contributing to a “Second Renaissance” (2024).

Based on these ideas, one can theorize that Dudash and DiCianni have the like-minded goal of encouraging a revival of Christian art that reflects the abundance of the Renaissance. During the Renaissance, the arts were not only used to preach, but to create a shared visual culture amongst believers. One of DiCianni’s most famous works, *The Resurrection Mural* (Figure 19), is a 12 x 40-foot mural that displays Christ emerging from the tomb, flanked by angels, ecstatic followers, and fainted Roman guards (DiCianni, 2024). This mural can serve both to inform and encourage those who do not know about the faith, as well as encourage those already part of the community, creating a shared visual culture. Similarly, Dudash’s religious work and signature can share his faith with others, as well as provide common ground for those already in the faith.

Conclusion of Discussion

This project, which draws upon the ideas of four art students and five professional artists, is by no means a generalization of all Christian artists' views. The analysis gleaned from this project relates to these particular artists and their personal viewpoints.

Understandably, professionals and students had some overlapping and some unique themes. For example, some art students and professional artists believe that art need not have religious imagery to be faith-based; faith-related concepts create art that is spiritual in thematic meaning (Students Sub-theme C, Professionals Theme C). Student 3, in particular, creates works with spiritual concepts, as does Lynn Aldrich.

Some students and professionals see art as a study of natural theology (Students Sub-theme A, Professionals Theme B). Both Kent Twitchell and Lynn Aldrich, as well as Student 3, seek to create art that reflects the reality of the universe we are situated in, celebrating its beauty. All artists reach this end differently; Twitchell paints murals of human figures, Aldrich creates sculptures using found objects, and Student 3 creates oil paintings of natural objects.

Another theme common to many of these students and professionals is the idea that art is a means of understanding transcendence (Students Theme A, Professionals Theme B). Lynn Aldrich emphasized the idea of the mundane becoming infused with an element of the divine, as her sculptures using mundane objects become art through her manipulation. Student 2 noted that the structure of cathedrals points upward, symbolizing heaven.

Interestingly, utilizing art as an evangelism tool was a more common sentiment among these professionals than among these students (Professionals Theme A, D, E). Makoto Fujimura and Kent Twitchell both use their artworks to integrate discussions of faith into the world in ways that are non-controversial for viewers with different beliefs. In Fujimura's case, his abstract

artworks with vague subject matter present a mainly calming viewing experience that allows the viewer's mind to create explanations; he does not provide a clear answer within his works, which are explained externally by their titles and his writings. Other artists, such as Michael Dudash and Ron DiCianni, paint faith-based imagery to share with audiences, directly evangelizing to all who see their works.

However, these students were committed to displaying their faith through artwork, usually conceptually. For example, Student 2 aims to utilize architecture to point to the divine, and Student 3 emphasizes death and resurrection symbolism in her work. Student 4 does create religious imagery but noted that it would likely be pertinent only to viewers who are of the same faith, so its usage as an evangelism tool would not be intentional.

This difference in ideas regarding evangelism may be caused by many factors. In the present project, no questions were asked that directly related to evangelism. There is the potential that, if interview questions directly related to this topic, students may have expressed interest in evangelizing with their works.

Overall, many of the art students and professional artists in this project overlapped in ideas of art as a study of natural theology, as a means of understanding transcendence, and as something that can be spiritual in concept, not solely imagery.

Conclusion

Upon analysis of interviews and professional artists' content, it is clear that there is a cyclical relationship between art and faith that progresses in a few distinct stages. Faith influences art, which is created and completed, after which art influences the faiths and/or spiritual ideas of viewers.

Firstly, faith influences the artmaking process and thus, the art created. This occurs in a few ways: for some artists, their faith influences them to create religious imagery; for others, their faith influences the concepts behind their art, whether visible or invisible.

The art itself, as an image and object, affects its viewers. The purposes of this artwork are multitudinous, spanning the range of inspiring audiences to understand transcendence, to provide good where it is lacking, to evangelize, to promote environmentalism inspired by faith. Intended audiences also play into these intended purposes, ranging from fellow Christians to the world at large. From these examples, it is more likely that artists creating direct religious imagery intend to display their work to those with religious backgrounds, while artists without religious imagery but with religious concepts intend their work to be shown to everyone.

Overall, the trend in thought via omission is that art is not valuable based on its physical constituents, but its deeper conceptual meaning, the ideologies that both go into it and result from it.

Throughout this project, my aim has been to gain insight into the purposes of art: the motivations that drive artists forward, and the goals and messages that they strive to convey. My primary questions are: What are the purposes of art, from the lens of current Christian artists? How does faith influence art, and vice versa?

The motivations behind this project are multifaceted. Firstly, documenting the ideas of Christian artists surrounding the purposes of art adds to the body of knowledge that has existed since the Old Testament, and has continued to the early catacombs, the medieval period, the Renaissance, and onward. Understanding how historical ideas of art changed with the Protestant Reformation served as a launchpad for the current project, which aims to document current

views. Adding to this body of knowledge also provides greater insight into the shared visual culture of current Christians, from the lens of these particular artists.

Overall, understanding how historical views on the purposes of art interacted with the kinds of art that were sanctioned, such as domestic art in Protestant households, served as a launching point for the current project to explore the way in which current Christian artist's views on the purposes of art influenced the types of art that they create, and how they intend for it to interact with the wider world. This analysis also serves as a reference point for artists to either begin or continue contemplating the motivations behind their own art. Art is a multidimensional process of reflecting on one's own beliefs, engaging with the process of artmaking, and interacting with the rest of the world; therefore, every viewpoint will be unique and add to the discussion on the multifaceted purpose of art.

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Figures

Figure 1: Fujimura, Makoto. (2011). *Charis-Kairos (Tears of Christ)*.

Figure 2: Twitchell, Kent. (1991/1993). *Harbor Freeway Overture*. Mural.

Figure 3: Twitchell, Kent. (1990). *The Word*. Mural.

Figure 4: Twitchell, Kent. (1984). *111th Street Jesus*. Mural.

Figure 5: Twitchell, Kent. (1977-1978). *Holy Trinity with the Virgin*. Mural.

Figure 6: Twitchell, Kent. (1971). *Six Los Angeles Artists*. Mural.

Figure 7: Aldrich, Lynn. (2015). *Water Feature*. Galvanized steel downspouts, exterior enamel.

Figure 8: DiCianni, Ron. *Safely Home*.

Figure 9: Fujimura, Makoto. (2021). *Walking on Water—Glacier*. Pulverized azurite and malachite on polished canvas, 84”x144”.

Figure 10: Fujimura, Makoto. (2021). *Lux Aeterna—Hope*. Red and refractive silver, with gold and azurite, on canvas.

Figure 11: Fujimura, Makoto. (2020). *Christmas, 3020*. Quartz, white ruby on azurite gesso on canvas. 89”x66”.

Figure 12: Aldrich, Lynn. (2023). *Free Refill*. Galvanized steel downspouts, exterior acrylic paint.

Figure 13: Aldrich, Lynn. (2007). *Biophilia*. Sponges, brushes, scrubbers, scouring pads, mop heads, plungers, plastic gloves, plumbing parts, wood.

Figure 14: Aldrich, Lynn. (2015). *Velvet Painting: Ascension*. Velvet, velveteen, plastic, wood.

Figure 15: Aldrich, Lynn. (2009). *Hydra Hydrant*. Plastic downspouts and elbows, leaf strainers, gutter parts.

Figure 16: Aldrich, Lynn. (2012). *Renew Your Reef* (left side). Brushes, scrubbers, sponges, scouring pads, gloves, mop heads, plungers, gloves, wood.

Figure 17: Dudash, Michael. (2021/2022). *Into an Autumn Wind*. Oil on linen, 12"x16".

Figure 18: Dudash, Michael. (1999). *Watching their Flocks by Night*. Oil on linen, 24"x40".

Figure 19: DiCianni, Ron. *The Resurrection Mural*. 12"x40".